

APPLICATIONS OF MATHEMATICS IN MANAGEMENT AND SCIENCES

Reena Tandon

Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics,
Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar, Punjab, India

ABSTRACT

The role of Mathematics in Management and Science programs (and Statistics to a smaller extent) was very less in earlier time. The impact of modern Mathematics and its application in other disciplines is presented from the 21st century historical perspective. In the early period, Mathematics grow innermost glance, and the distinction between pure and applied Mathematics became much more pronounced and there was a return to more classical topics but on a new level and this resulted in a new convergence between Mathematics and physics. The 21st century move toward to Mathematics resulted in a more developed Mathematical language, new powerful Mathematical tools, and inspired new application areas that have resulted in tremendous discoveries in other applied sciences. Towards the end of the 21st Century, Mathematicians were making a re-think on the need to bridge the division lines within Mathematics, to open up more for other disciplines and to promote the line of inter-discipline research. The current cry is that this interaction will be further strengthened in future. This paper focuses on certain factors that may be attributed for the students showing disinterest in Mathematics. However, to achieve the objective of enhancing the students' Mathematical ability, there is a need of effective use of teaching methodology. This paper gives an overview of applications of Mathemtics and its importance in different fields.

Key words: Significance of Mathematics. Effective teaching methodology,
Methodologies practiced

1. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics has a key role to play in the development of a modern high technolgy economy. It is essential to create an awreness of the value of Mathematics not only as an intellectual discipline in itself but also in terms of its contribution to the genertation of higher living standards and more jobs. It has been vital to the development of civilization. From ancient to modern times, Mathematics has been fundamental to advances in science, engineering, and philosophy. A number of motivations that can be categorised have driven developments in modern Mathematics into the solution of a difficult problem and the creation of new theory

enlarging the fields of applications of Mathematics. Very often, the solution of a concrete difficult problem is based on the creation of a new Mathematical theory. This paper is discussing the application of Mathematics in Management & Sciences .

2 .DEVIATION OF MATHEMATICS FROM PHYSICS

Mathematicians concentrated around problems of algebraic topology, algebraic geometry and complex analysis and they developed new concepts and new methods. New powerful Mathematical tools were developed and the language of Mathematics became highly developed and very powerful. This had great impact on diverse fields such as number theory, set theory, geometry, topology and partial differential equations. This new approach to Mathematics resulted in greater abstraction. Mathematicians spent years of apprenticeship in a full set of abstraction before doing their own thinking. When the basics were clear, enough there was a search for powerful tools that allowed for development and expansion of the geometric intuition into new domains. Examples are topology, homological algebra and algebraic geometry. These new developments made it possible for great breakthroughs in solving several difficult problems that were stuck .

Because of the new approach to Mathematics, pure mathematicians drifted away from applications and saw no need to collaborate with other scientists, even their traditional neighbours, and the physicists. On the other hand, application of the highly abstract modern Mathematics could not be easily visualised by the traditional users of Mathematics. Mathematics became inward looking, and the distinction between pure and applied mathematics became much more pronounced. The diversification of Mathematics was first connected with external social phenomenon, the rapid growth of the scientific community and the breaking discoveries in physics .

The traditional area of application of Mathematics is physics. Within this area, the deepest mathematics and success stories have been achieved. For example, Einstein's general theory of relativity was based on classical differential geometry of Riemannian spaces, the Hilbert spaces, the theory of linear operators, and spectral theory. The connection of Mathematics and other sciences, especially physics was broken. Physicists got interested in solving more concrete problems that could be solved without the application of sophisticated and abstract modern Mathematics. The developments of pure mathematics in the post World War II period became weakly connected with applied sciences especially physics. Mathematicians' could not view how Physics could assist modern Mathematics while Physicist could not imagine the application of new abstract Mathematical concepts such as sheaf, cohomology, J- functor and the like in their fields .

2.1 Re-Convergence of Mathematics with Physics

Some modern Mathematicians quickly saw new opportunities and challenges hidden in the new physics. Examples of Mathematical results that got inspired by physical ideas include Donaldson's proof of the existence of different differential structures on simply connected 4-dimensional manifolds. This has very deep consequences for quantum gravity and the gauge theory on strong and weak interactions and resulted in the revisit of the Yang-Mills equations of elementary particles. The Yang-Mills equations had been considered non-physical and had attracted very little attention of physicists. Structures in the elementary particles are described by highly nonlinear equations with deep topological properties. The new conservation laws developed are believed to be the most fundamental in physics. Most success stories of application of pure, most abstract mathematics are in physics. The application of modern abstract Mathematics in physics has resulted in astounding discoveries in the physical sciences, the life sciences and technology .

The new approach to Mathematics resulted in a more developed Mathematical language, new powerful Mathematical tools, and inspired new application areas that have resulted in tremendous discoveries in other applied sciences including computer science and computer technology. The new Mathematical tools and the developments in computer technology, the development of algorithms, Mathematical modelling and scientific computing have led to remarkable new discoveries in physics, technology, economics and other sciences. This has also enabled Mathematicians to use modern Mathematical tools to solve deep classical problems left by the previous generation of Mathematicians .

2. APPLICATION OF MATHEMATICS IN SCIENCE

The branch of Mathematics traditionally used in the applications in physics is analysis and differential geometry. Most of the advances in pure Mathematics were propelled by problems in physics. The tools of Mathematical analysis and differential geometry was no longer adequate. For example, a biologist trying to understand the genetic code will need tools of graph theory than differential equations because the genetic code is discrete. Issues of information content, redundancy or stability of the code are more likely to find tools of theoretical computer science useful than those of classical Mathematics are. Even in physics, discrete systems such as elementary particles need use of combinatorial tools and statistical mechanics need tools of graph theory and probability theory. Traditionally economics is a heavy user of applied Mathematics toolbox .

Now economics utilises sophisticated Mathematics in operations research such as linear programming, integer programming and other combinatorial optimisation models.

3.1 Mathematics in Materials Sciences

Materials sciences is concerned with the synthesis and manufacture of new materials, the modification of materials, the understanding and prediction of material properties, and the evolution and control of these properties over a time period. Until recently, materials science was primarily an empirical study in metallurgy, ceramics, and plastics. Today it is a vast growing body of knowledge based on physical sciences, engineering, and Mathematics .

For example, Mathematical models are emerging quite reliable in the synthesis and manufacture of polymers. Some of these models are based on statistics or statistical mechanics and others are based on a diffusion equation in finite or infinite dimensional spaces. Simpler but more phenomenological models of polymers are based on Continuum Mechanics with added terms to account for ‘memory.’ Stability and singularity of solutions are important issues for materials scientists. The Mathematics is still lacking even for these simpler models .

Another example is the study of composites. Motor companies, for example, are working with composites of aluminium and silicon-carbon grains, which provide lightweight alternative to steel. Fluid with magnetic particles or electrically charged particles will enhance the effects of brake fluid and shock absorbers in the car. Over the last decade, Mathematicians have developed new tools in functional analysis, PDE, and numerical analysis, by which they have been able to estimate or compute the effective properties of composites. But the list of new composites is ever increasing and new materials are constantly being developed. These will continue to need Mathematical input .

Another example is the study of the formation of cracks in materials. When a uniform elastic body is subjected to high pressure, cracks will form. Where and how the cracks initiate, how they evolve, and when they branch out into several cracks are questions that are still being researched .

3.2 Mathematics in Biology

Mathematical models are also emerging in the biological and medical sciences. For example in physiology, consider the kidney. One million tiny tubes around the kidney, called nephrons, have the task of absorbing salt from the blood into the kidney. They do it through contact with blood vessels by a transport process in which osmotic pressure and filtration play a role. Biologists have identified the body tissues and substances, which are involved in this process, but the precise rules of the process, are only barely understood. A simple mathematical model of the renal process shed some light on the formation of urine and on decisions made by the kidney on whether, for example, to excrete a large volume of diluted urine or a small volume of

concentrated urine. A more complete model may include PDE, stochastic equations, fluid dynamics, elasticity theory, filtering theory, control theory, and perhaps other tools.

Other topics in physiology where recent mathematical studies have already made some progress include heart dynamics, calcium dynamics, the auditory process, cell adhesion and motility (vital for physiological processes such as inflammation and wound healing) and bio-fluids. Other areas where mathematics is poised to make important progress include the growth process in general and embryology in particular, cell signalling, immunology, emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases, and ecological issues such as global phenomena in vegetation, modelling animal grouping and the human brain .

4. APPLICATIONS OF MATHEMATICS IN MANAGEMENT

The **21st century** made a rethink on the foundations of Mathematics, it was characterised by a new approach to Mathematics, Hilbert's vision was to analyse axioms of each subject and state results in their full generality. Parallel trends took place in functional analysis with Banach Spaces. This spread rapidly to algebraic topology, harmonic analysis and partial differential equations. In addition to this axiomatic approach, the Bourbaki group introduced the idea that there was one universal set of definitions, which once learnt, would be the foundations of everything more specialized .

4.1 Importance of Business Mathematics in Management

Mathematics is an important subject and knowledge of it enhances a person's reasoning, problem-solving skills, and in general, the ability to think. Hence it is important for understanding almost every subject whether science and technology, medicine, the economy, or business and finance. Mathematical tools such as the theory of chaos are used to mapping market trends and forecasting of the same. Statistics and probability that are branches of Mathematics are used in everyday business and economics. Mathematics also forms an important part of accounting, and many accountancy companies prefer graduates with joint degrees with Mathematics rather than just an accountancy qualification. Financial Mathematics and Business Mathematics form two important branches of Mathematics in today's world and these are direct application of Mathematics to business and economics. Examples of applied Maths such as probability theory and management science, such as queuing theory, time-series analysis, linear programming all are vital Maths for business .

"Importance of Business Mathematics in Management" is sometimes called commercial math or consumer math, is a group of practical subjects used in commerce and everyday life. Business Mathematics in management system is able to make more effective in some cases by use of more advanced mathematics such as calculus, matrix algebra and linear programming. Business organizations use mathematics in accounting, inventory management, marketing, sales

forecasting, financial analysis etc. Importance of Mathematics in Management System is a scheme of Business Management.

4.2 Significance of Mathematics in Management Science

The emerging problems in Industry require the techniques of Operations research, which is one of the modern areas of application of Mathematics. It has become imperative for managers to take the decisions on the calculations based on scientific principles, rather than deciding on the basis of intuitions. Every person needs to take correct decisions in his/her businesses or fields and he/she may be an Economist, Industrialist, Financial Analysts, Human Resource manager or a common businessman. Management Science is the science for managing and helps in the process decision – making. The use of Mathematics in Management science started during Second World War to solve military and defense problems. In turn, this created faith that Mathematics could be applied successfully to any human endeavor and could yield valuable results. After Second World War, intensive efforts were made all over the world to Mathematize many new areas of human activity and faith grew that Mathematics could have significant application in Biological, Social and Management Science. Management science focuses specifically on the development of mathematical models. These models help organizations to try out various activities with the use of a computer. Some of the fields which are included in Management Science are Decision Analysis, Optimization, Simulation, Forecasting, Game Theory, Network Modeling, Transportation, Mathematical Modeling, Data Mining, Probability and Statistics and Quantitative Methods .

Most common functions used in business are supply and demand functions, cost functions, profit function, revenue function, production function, utility function etc which is a part of Applied Mathematics.

It is very interesting to know that how Mathematics is related to other fields of Management. Statistics, be it Descriptive or Inferential Statistics, it is related to Mathematics whereas modern theory of Statistics is based on probability measures. Operations management helps organizations develop techniques to produce their products and services more efficiently through the extensive use of Operations Research techniques, which is considered an important branch of Applied Mathematics. Finance sectors use Mathematics to calculate the time value of money. It is used in Actuarial Science to calculate the overall investments, to discover how systematic and unsystematic risk affects the stock valuation. In addition, commissions and odds can be calculated, price-to-earnings ratios may be compared, the results of various investment strategies can be graphed for comparison of the bond values, net asset value and the return on investment can be calculated .

Economics was the first Social Science to be developed mathematically. Mathematics is the language used by economist. Infact Econometrics is a highly developed Mathematical

Science. Most of the Noble prizes in Economics have gone to those who have worked Mathematical problems on Economics. Economic activities involve functions of more than one independent variable so it becomes inevitable to measure the effect of a change in the independent variables on the dependent variable in a multivariate function. The objective of the economist is to measure the risk; to decide the quantity of risk to be handled and to find out methods to eliminate unwanted risk by taking proper actions. To serve the objective of Management courses, certain topics of Mathematics are suggested as the prerequisites. Those topics are functions, linear algebra, set theory, matrix algebra, differentiation and applications of derivatives, integration and probability .

5. APPLICATION OF MATHEMATICS IN OTHER FIELDS

5.1 Mathematics in Digital Technology

The Mathematics of multimedia encompasses a wide range of research areas, which include computer vision, image processing, speech recognition and language understanding, computer aided design, and new modes of networking. The Mathematical tools in multimedia may include stochastic processes, Markov fields, statistical patterns, decision theory, PDE, numerical analysis, graph theory, graphic algorithms, image analysis and wavelets, and many others. Computer aided design is becoming a powerful tool in many industries. This technology is a potential area for research Mathematicians. The future of the World Wide Web (www) will depend on the development of many new Mathematical ideas and algorithms, and Mathematicians will have to develop ever more secure cryptographic schemes and thus new developments from number theory, discrete Mathematics, algebraic geometry, and dynamical systems, as well as other fields .

5.2 Mathematics in the Army

Recent trends in mathematics research in the USA Army have been influenced by lessons learnt during combat in Bosnia. The USA army could not bring heavy tanks in time and helicopters were not used to avoid casualty. Also there is need for lighter systems with same or improved requirement as before. Breakthroughs are urgently needed and mathematics research is being funded with a hope to get the urgently needed systems. These future automated systems are complex and nonlinear, they will likely be multiple units, small in size, light in weight, very efficient in energy utilisation and extremely fast in speed and will likely be self-organised and self coordinated to perform special tasks .

5.3 Bridging the Division Lines

Developments in computer technology have re-activated some areas in the fields of discrete mathematics, formal logic and probability that were otherwise dormant for a long time. Examples include the vast and rapid developments in the areas of algorithms, databases, formal

languages, as well as cryptography and computer security. Just about 25 years ago questions in number theory that seemed to belong to the purest, most classical and completely in applicable mathematics now belong to the core of mathematical cryptology and computer security.

5.4 Potential Contribution to Other Fields

As evidenced by the discoveries, Mathematics can enrich not only physics and the other physical sciences, but also medicine and the biomedical sciences and engineering. It can also play a role in such practical matters as how to speed the flow of traffic on the Internet or sharpen the transmission of digitised images, how to better understand and possibly predict patterns in the stock market, how to gain insights into human behaviour, and even how to enrich the entertainment world through contributions to digital technology .

Through Mathematical modelling, numerical experiments, analytical studies and other Mathematical techniques, mathematics can make enormous contributions to many fields. Mathematics has to do with human genes, the world of finance and geometric motions. For example, science now has a huge body of genetic information, and researchers need mathematical methods and algorithms to search the data as well as clustering methods and computer models (among others) to interpret the data. Finance is very mathematical; it has to do with derivatives, risk management, portfolio management and stock options. All these are modelled mathematically, and consequently Mathematicians are having a real impact on how those businesses are evolving. Motion driven by the geometry of interfaces is omnipresent in many areas of science from growing crystals for manufacturing semiconductors to tracking tumours in biomedical images. The convergence of Mathematics and the life sciences, which was not foreseen a generation ago, is a tremendous opportunity for application .

5.5 Inter-Discipline Mathematics

Currently, efforts are being undertaken to facilitate collaborative research across traditional academic fields and to help train a new generation of interdisciplinary mathematicians and scientists. In addition, similar efforts are slowly being introduced in undergraduate and postgraduate. Mathematics curricula and pedagogy. Disciplines that hitherto hardly used mathematics in their curricula are now demanding substantial doses of knowledge of and skills in mathematics. For example the pre-requisites for mathematical knowledge and skills for entry in into biological and other life sciences as well as the mathematics content in the university curricula of these programmes is becoming quite substantial. Curricula for the social sciences programmes now include sophisticated mathematics over and above the traditional descriptive statistics. Curricula of some universities in the developed countries have inter-disciplinary programmes where mathematics students and students from other sciences (including social sciences) work jointly on projects. The aim is to prepare graduates for the new approaches and practices in their fields and careers .

5.6 Inter-disciplines in Research

Complexity theory is an example of inter-discipline and is the new focus on research in Mathematics .Certain essential details of complexity have been known for quite some time. At the end of the 19th century, the first source of a general idea of complex systems was research in dynamical systems, in the context of classical mechanics. It is an interdisciplinary approach fuelled by sophisticated mathematics, mathematical modelling and computer simulation, inspired by observations made on complex systems in the most diverse fields including meteorology, climate research, ecology, economics, physics, embryology, computer networks and many more. Examples are systems that adapt to changes in their environment in an extremely surprising way. They include Economics (economy of a country), Biodiversity (ecosystem of a pond), Biology (the immune system of an organism) and Artificial Intelligence (Computer Networks).

Probability theory seems to bridge most of the division lines within mathematics. The importance of probabilistic methods in almost all areas of mathematics is exploding. Probability theory is one illustration of the unity of mathematics that goes deeper than just using tools from other branches of mathematics. With probability theory, many basic questions can be modelled as discrete or as continuous problems .

CONCLUSION

During the last 50 years, developments in Mathematics, in computing and communication technologies have made it possible for most of the breath taking discoveries in basic sciences, for the tremendous innovations and inventions in engineering sciences and technology and for the great achievements and breakthroughs in economics and life sciences. These have led to the emergency of many new areas of Mathematics and enabled areas that were dormant to explode. Now every branch of Mathematics has a potential for applicability in other fields of Mathematics and other disciplines. All these, have posed a big challenge on the Mathematics curricula at all levels of the education systems, teacher preparation and pedagogy. The 21st Century Mathematics thinking is to further strengthen efforts to bridge the division lines within Mathematics, to open up more for other disciplines and to foster the line of inter-discipline research .

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://mathematics.blurtit.com/q420028.html>
- [2] <http://math.about.com/library/weekly/aa101103a.htm>
- [3] Brechner, Robert. (2006). Contemporary Mathematics for Business and Consumers, Thomson South-Western.

[4]Wegner, Trevor. (2010). Applied Business Statistics: Methods and Excel-Based Applications, Juta Academic.

Books

1. James Dr. Anice (2006), “Techniques of Teaching Mathematics”, Neelkamal Publications Pvt Ltd, pp 9-10
2. J.N. Kapur(1994-95), “Fascinating world of Mathematical Sciences, Applications of Mathematics”, Vol. 2, Published by Miss K. Kapur for Mathematical Science Trust Society, New Delhi, , pp 126-129
3. Prasad B. K.(2002), Encyclopedia of “Teaching of Commerce and Business Management”, published by Anmol Publications Pvt Ltd, New Delhi, 1st Edition, pp 713-738
4. Vijay Kumar S. J.& D. Bhaskar Rao(2006), “Techniques of Teaching Mathematics”, published by Sonali Publications, New Delhi, p 36